

Identifying Differential Item Functioning in Polytomous Items with Logistic Discriminant Analysis

Abstract

Logistic discriminant analysis (LDA) combined with item difficulty difference was used to identify differential item functioning (DIF) in polytomous items. The LDA-based method has well-controlled type I error rate and high power, even when there is missing scoring category.

Summary

Introduction

The use of polytomous items requires reconsideration of differential item functioning (DIF) identification procedure. A few methods, namely Welch t-test, Mantel-Haenszel, logistic regression, and logistic discriminant analysis (LDA) (Linacre, 2022; Spray & Miller, 1993; Su & Wang, 2005), have been generalized and developed for polytomous item DIF identification. Among them, LDA is a promising method as it has high sensitivity and is formatted simpler than logistic regression for polytomous items. In testing practice, we are only concerned about DIF that is of considerable size. Thus, the high power of LDA in detecting small DIF is not desirable (Spray & Miller, 1994). In this way, adding practical effect size criterion would benefit the DIF identification (Gómez-Benito, Hidalgo, & Zumbo, 2013). Moreover, Welch t-test and Mantel-Haenszel can't handle missing response category well and tend to produce nonsensible results. In this study, LDA combined with item difficulty difference was proposed for polytomous item DIF identification. Welch t-test and contrast combination as used in WINSTEPS was employed as a reference to evaluate the performance of the LDA-based method.

Method

Review of Welch t-test in WINSTEPS

First, focal group and reference group responses are combined for item calibration. Based on the combined group item parameter, compute the offset of each group parameters. Then a Welch t-test is conducted on the offsets of focal group and reference group. The standard error of the t-test is computed based on the sample sizes and the standard error of estimate of the offsets. Only when the Welch t-test is significant and the contrast (difference between the two offsets) is larger than 0.5, the item is identified as having DIF.

Development of LDA-based method

When used for DIF identification, LDA treats grouping as the dependent variable. Equation (1) is the full model.

$$P(G_i|\theta_i, x_{ij}) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\beta_0 - \beta_1\theta_i - \beta_2x_{ij} - \beta_3\theta_ix_{ij})} \quad (1)$$

θ_i is the ability of candidate i , x_{ij} is the response of candidate i to item j , and G_i is the grouping of candidate i . In DIF detecting, G_i only has two values, denoting reference group and focal group. As uniform DIF is common and have more practical implications, only uniform DIF (β_2) is of concern in this study. Non-uniform DIF (β_3) is treated as a covariate. In model comparison, the full model is as shown in equation (1) and the no uniform DIF model is shown in equation (2):

$$P(G_i|\theta_i, x_{ij}) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\beta_0 - \beta_1\theta_i - \beta_3\theta_ix_{ij})} \quad (2)$$

Item difficulty difference is used as practical effect size measure for LDA. It is the difference between the two sets of items parameters that are separately estimated for focal group and reference group. Only when the full model is significantly better than the no uniform model and the difference between item difficulties is larger than 0.5 (analogue to the contrast criterion in Welch t-test), would the item be identified as having DIF.

Simulation Study

A simulation study was conducted to compare the performance of Welch t-test combined with contrast and the LDA combined with item difficulty difference. Partial credit model was employed. The sample size of the reference group and focal group are 400 and 200. Candidates from both groups were generated from a standard normal distribution. Three missing types were considered: both groups miss category 0, only focal group miss category 0, and no missing. To generate the responses with missing category, the item responses were over simulated, then responses of certain category were removed until the number of remaining responses met the sample size requirement. Reference group item thresholds were set to be (-2.5, -1, 0). A no DIF condition and a DIF size of 0.5 logit condition (focal group item thresholds are 0.5 larger than those of reference group) were used to evaluate both type I error rate and power. 100 repetitions were done to obtain robust results. The true theta values were used in both Welch t-test and LDA.

Results

As shown in Figure 1, both Welch t-test and LDA-based method have well-controlled type I error rates. Figure 2 shows, when there's no missing scoring category or both groups have missing, both methods have power around 0.5. As the DIF size is same to the practical effect size criteria, 0.5 logit of contrast or item difficulty difference, we would expect half of the time the DIF can be identified. When focal group miss category 0, Welch method has very low power, while LDA shows considerably high power. This is a outstanding advantage of the LDA-based method.

Figure 1. Type I error rate of DIF identification

Figure 2. Power of DIF identification

References

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